

Transforming Data Management in Telecommunications: the Case Study of OTE Group’s Integration with DATAMITE project*

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Abstract. This paper presents an innovative framework that aims to adapt data management within the telecommunication sector in the rapidly evolving AI era. It deals with the challenge of managing large amounts of data by a group of companies consisting of various subsidiaries, systems, and data lakes. A modular open-source approach is proposed to enhance data monetization, interoperability, trading, and exchange, weighing the demands of the telecommunication industry against the services offered by the framework. The article discusses three prevalent use case scenarios that are mainly encountered in Business-As-Usual working activities: OLAP queries that are predominantly set up in data warehouses, visual and strategic analysis discovery for planning and decision-making, and OLTP processes for daily scanning and monitoring of products, solutions, and resources. Finally, it charts a transformation deployment plan that aligns the existing data architecture with the DATAMITE project’s vision, moving away from the traditional two-tier model towards a much more flexible, data product-focused design.

Keywords: DATAMITE project · Data management · Interoperability · Telecommunications

1 Introduction

OTE Group [17] manages an extensive volume of data and has a dominant position in the telecommunications sector in Greece. Historically, the organization has been leading the landline communication operations and has played a crucial

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role in the country’s transition to digital infrastructure. During the early stages of digitization, landlines were not only central to communication but also served as identifiers for unique services and physical locations, thus establishing a link between digital services and geographical or residential identities.

During the past two decades, the OTE Group has significantly expanded its telecommunication operations, introducing a variety of technical services and assets that extend beyond telecoms. Nowadays, these offerings contain a wide range of digital interactions, facilitating seamless engagement between customers, businesses, and the public sector. However, this fast expansion required the integration and interoperability of a diverse type of services to deliver personalized and value-added experiences to customers.

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into all levels of organizational processes fundamentally reshapes operational models. Telecom operators, including OTE Group, are uniquely positioned to expand their service offerings by leveraging the vast amounts of data they host [18, 10]. This data can be utilized not only to develop new services, but also to refine and optimize existing processes and products. The rationale behind this transformation is that AI effectiveness is strongly related to data availability. In fact, the large repositories maintained by organizations represent an asset to generate valuable insights and create innovative solutions [4]. However, harnessing this potential requires a robust information life cycle management framework [14] and a clear vision. This is where the DATAMITE project [6] starts, aiming to address the opportunities but also the challenges [9] of data monetization for European organizations, by offering a modular, open-source, and multi-domain framework to improve Data Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading, and Exchange, empowering companies to become new relevant players in the data economy.

The rest of the document is structured as follows. Section 2 summarizes the related literature, while section 3 introduces the current challenges faced by OTE Group, concerning data management. Next, section 4 describes in detail the use case scenarios, and in section 5 the proposed solution is analyzed. Finally, section 6 concludes the paper, also presenting a brief plan for future work.

2 Related Work

In recent years, much research effort has been spent to explore the impact of swiftly evolving technologies like big data and AI in the telecommunications domain. More specifically, studies have proven that Big Data Analytics (BDA) show a significant influence on the decision-making of the companies in the domain [1]. In addition, the successful implementation of BDA can lead to improved service quality, real-time monitoring of call data records to detect anomalies, and optimized call routing [12]. On the other hand, AI enables telecom industries to improve their ability to proactively analyze customer behavior and their service choices [7]. In fact, the role of machine learning and AI algorithms is crucial to predict customer churn thus enhancing clients’ retention [2]. Following this trend, big players in the domain have already shifted their services accordingly.

For instance, AT&T has made substantial investments in the research and development of 5G network technologies based on AI, to exploit the massive amounts of data they manage. Moreover, British Telecom Group employs data analytics to improve their operation, including optimizing call center functionalities and predicting service faults [11].

3 Problem Statement

OTE Group includes many subsidiaries, which currently have their own data repositories (either served by Data Warehouse and/or Data Lake) that mainly ingest, store, process and analyze their own datasets. Each subsidiary has its own data model (often not well-structured), data catalog, their development, architectural standards, and operations processes. When a subsidiary needs information that is not part of its own business, a data exchange process is initiated to request data based on the business need. Then data availability is validated by the data business owner and a sample data is shared with the data requester to validate business usage and data quality. Security and privacy related directions (i.e., General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)) are aligned, and the data integration process begins in order for the target system to receive fresh datasets on the commonly agreed time frame, and also these datasets are being processed accordingly to fit into the target system process. The data model is then introduced in the data catalog.

	Current Challenges	Expected Benefits
Usage	Combine data from different sources & different granularity is not straightforward.	Query data in a federated manner.
Governance	Data is dispersed across different systems, which makes difficulty to identify the data owner in efficient way.	Metadata located in centralized repository, reducing complexity of governing data (data ownership / data definition / data mapping).
Semantic Interoperability	Different sources have different models and their integration to a unique one is difficult and time consuming.	A unique data model across organization with global mapping to correlate main entity identifiers across data sources.
Quality	Data quality checks implemented only in the consumption point (reactive checks), and issue resolution takes time & effort (ad-hoc analysis).	Global point to define data quality rules on top of data source models and quality reports are available prior usage (pro-active checks).
Security	Access controls & monitoring are implemented across all systems and integration points.	Centralized layer for uniform, fine grain and rule-based security controls.

Fig. 1. Current challenges and expected benefits from DATAMITE

In general, that data exchange process is lengthy, complex, and resource demanding, resulting in data and process duplication (which increases the overall infrastructure needs), in increased delivery times, and last but not least in huge development and operational efforts. Within a large-scale data environment, such challenges (Figure 1) can lead to logical inconsistencies that can trigger cascading

failures, which require substantial time and resources to mitigate. Furthermore, these discrepancies can occasionally propagate to end-users, negatively affecting the customer experience, which is a critical factor in the highly competitive telecommunications sector.

Further complicating the situation is the constant influx of new services and shifting objectives of organizational units, driven by the evolving market. These changes need much flexibility to remain competitive and State-of-the-Art. Current solutions, which are often based on traditional models and architectures from the past two decades, face significant shortcomings. More specifically, they are not AI-enabled and do not incorporate features that are essential for modern data management. Furthermore, the DevSecOps paradigm [19] has transformed the way companies manage data, creating the need for structural rather than superficial changes. A middleware that automates or semi-automates data integration is crucial in addressing those challenges. In addition, a unified query language is essential to ensure sustainability and usability across the organization. Simplifying the learning curve and minimizing training requirements are critical in a fast-paced market where rapid adaptation is necessary.

To gain competitiveness, organizations must focus on developing a unified platform capable of supporting diverse Data Warehouse architectures, while implementing a standardized, user-friendly programming language to streamline database interactions. Ensuring security and enabling efficient development of Data Marts that can be readily distributed to analysts for detailed examination is also vital. In addition, it is essential to support high-performance processing of both Online Analytical Processing (OLAP) and Online Transaction Processing (OLTP) workloads [20], incorporate AI capabilities to expose metadata and features for modern applications, and present these capabilities through an intuitive and comprehensive Graphical User Interface (GUI) where critical information is easily accessible.

4 Use Case Scenarios

As the complexity of data schemas increases, the implementation of quality controls becomes essential. Inconsistencies within different repositories cause severe problems in system operations that consequently disrupt the enterprise workflow. This issue is particularly critical for the Customer Experience (CX) department, which relies on accurate and reliable data to deliver personalized services at competitive prices, to satisfy current customers and potentially attract new ones.

In fact, CX is an aspect in which big industries invest substantial resources throughout the customer journey. Any disruptions or errors arising from inconsistencies in the data may destroy customer trust and satisfaction, ultimately jeopardizing the organization's efforts to maintain long-term, cooperative relationships with its clients.

The following subsections analyze the different test scenarios against which the solution proposed in this paper has been validated.

4.1 OLAP Dimension

The first scenario involves the development of dedicated Data Marts [13] that integrate information from various repositories to enable data analysts to identify inconsistencies and modify tables to ensure accuracy and alignment across all departments. In this case, the Data Governance department is responsible for creating a Data Mart considering critical factors, such as the repositories where inconsistencies may exist, complaints from customers or employees concerning inaccurate data, as well as quality metadata derived from those tables. All of these processes are performed in accordance with security and privacy protocols.

The core concept is to provide periodic snapshots of data, allowing analysts to identify inconsistencies and derive rules that enforce conformity across repositories. This Data Mart is distributed to analysts, who then investigate discrepancies within specific views of the repositories. The insights generated from this analysis are subsequently sent to the Data Compliance department for validation. There, these insights are examined to ensure that they are accurate, do not duplicate existing rules, and are not already addressed by other mechanisms. After being revised in consultation with the relevant departments, the new rules are applied in the production environment, leading to updates in the data repositories to resolve the identified inconsistencies.

The scenario is actually a direct application of DevOps principles to data management, providing secure and systematic pipelines for Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) in the data domain. The data mesh approach is followed towards a Data Space environment [5], which ensures consistent compliance with emerging EU regulations and strategies for data exposure. This structured methodology enhances data accuracy, interoperability, and scalability in complex data environments.

4.2 Visual and Strategic Dimension

The second scenario attempts to address the challenges of identifying correlations between data repositories, taking advantage of metadata analysis. In this approach, data scientists and architects use advanced metadata to identify potential sources of inconsistencies and their root causes. The primary goal is to strategically prioritize Data Warehouses and organizational departments that require immediate attention.

This prioritization [15] may be driven by strategic decisions, such as where to concentrate the efforts in order to maximize the enterprise's revenue, how to improve customer relationships by enhancing customer success stories and satisfaction, or how to reduce complaints and avoid potential fines arising from inaccurate database information. Following this strategy, the company ensures that its resources are optimally allocated to address the most critical aspects, which have the greatest impact on its organizational goals.

A key point of this scenario is the use of visual analytics to explore various cases and identify unique characteristics. Visual representations of metadata and insights provide a comprehensive overview that helps to understand complex

relationships and patterns across repositories. This visual approach is particularly significant when presenting findings and strategies to the upper management of the company. Clear and engaging visualizations ensure that metadata insights, data inconsistencies, and strategic guidelines are communicated effectively, aligning technical analysis with the broader objectives of the company, thus facilitating informed decision-making.

By coupling metadata exploration with visual analytics and aligning findings with strategic objectives, this scenario puts emphasis on optimizing Data Warehouse management and ensuring that the enterprise remains agile and competitive in a data-driven environment.

4.3 OLTP Dimension

The third scenario deals with the day-to-day operations of the company, where the need for accurate, real-time solutions is critical. In this context, it is vital to ensure that instant changes can be made without being impeded by security or technical restrictions. This process requires personnel with appropriate rights to modify data, coming from multiple sources to resolve specific issues or inconsistencies as they are detected.

A major pain point for OTE Group is that its customer data is stored in various IT systems, making it difficult to create a unified view to fully support the strategy defined by the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) department. This unified view is needed to optimize sales, services, and marketing processes. Consequently, the implementation of a continuous customer data improvement and quality assurance process within a centralized customer view is crucial to ensuring consistent and reliable data throughout the enterprise.

In this scenario, like the OLAP dimension one, the ideal solution involves the use of a middleware platform capable of adhering to regulatory restrictions while providing a standardized environment. With this platform, employees can perform standardized queries, preferably using Structured Query Language (SQL), to manage daily processes and correct misinformation or errors effectively. Such an environment would allow for real-time adjustments without compromising compliance or security.

This capability especially applies when the company seeks to attract new customers or provide additional services to existing ones based on established relationships. Human involvement is still important in this process, since experienced personnel can identify and resolve logical issues that automated systems might ignore. For example, during the preparation of an offer or while analyzing a customer profile, any errors or inconsistencies, could be promptly corrected. This proactive approach helps to prevent potential customer dissatisfaction, so that CX remains positive thus protecting the enterprise's relationship with its clients.

The integration of real-time correction capabilities with robust middleware along with a unified customer view improves operational efficiency and strengthens the organization's ability to respond dynamically to both internal needs and customer demands.

5 Solution Implementation

The dynamic landscape of modern applications and data management necessitates a paradigm change towards a data-centric approach, according to which data is the primary asset, and all supporting infrastructures serve to facilitate its efficient utilization. The DATAMITE framework [3] aligns with this vision by establishing a structured and secure data exchange ecosystem that prioritizes data governance, quality assurance, and regulatory compliance.

One of the core objectives of DATAMITE is to provide a set of open-source modules for data governance, quality, and security that can be easily integrated with existing systems and also customized to fit to any company’s peculiarities. This enables organizations to enforce fine-grained Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) while maintaining a centralized architecture for defining and managing data quality standards.

The Data Governance module of DATAMITE acts as a unifying layer, ensuring a consistent interpretation of business terminology across diverse data sources for both technical and business users. Furthermore, the Data Quality module enforces predefined freshness and accuracy standards, thereby boosting confidence in the usability and reliability of datasets. Moreover, the Security and Data Sharing modules facilitate secure and transparent data exchange, ensuring adherence to GDPR as well as to national and internal security policies via a centralized framework.

To evaluate the actual impact and effectiveness of DATAMITE, its performance should be validated against a use case that integrates multiple heterogeneous data platforms and delivers tangible business value. A representative example of such kind of use cases is the *Predict Next Billing Interaction* scenario. The goal of the scenario is to identify customers who are likely to contact call centers regarding billing issues (e.g., bill shock) after receiving an invoice. By proactively detecting those cases, the organization can initiate preventive engagement strategies, ultimately improving customer satisfaction and retention.

5.1 Existing Data Management Architecture

DATAMITE framework provides an integrated and secure data exchange environment, to enable organizations to unlock new data-driven insights, improve decision-making, and ensure regulatory compliance in an increasingly complex data landscape. The integration of OTE Group’s data architecture with the DATAMITE framework is achieved by aligning the existing Data Mart structure of OTE’s traditional model with the **Data Product paradigm** introduced by DATAMITE. This transition is not only compatible but also in accordance to the European Union’s vision for Data Spaces, enhancing interoperability, security, and efficiency. OTE’s existing model for data-driven applications and services is structured around a two-layer approach (Figure 2).

The first layer is responsible for optimizing data storage by organizing data in a well-structured Data Mart derived from OTE’s Data Lake. That kind of Data Marts are designed to cover specific business objectives, particularly to

Fig. 2. Existing two-layer approach model

support analysts and decision-makers. To ensure consistency and accessibility, it is governed by a policy engine and library that transforms it into a structured and consumable product. Once structured, it becomes available through an internal Data Mart marketplace. There, the employees with the necessary rights can discover it and request to access it according to their needs.

The second layer governs access to those Data Marts through RBAC, ensuring that query results are tailored based on the user's role. When an employee retrieves a Data Mart, they can apply designated AI algorithms or conduct analytical queries on the dataset. At this stage, additional security layers verify that the user has the required credentials and authentication privileges before granting access to sensitive data. This approach enhances privacy and security and aligns with organizational policies.

While this model is effective in ensuring data security and compliance, it presents significant limitations in terms of flexibility and quick prototyping. Decision-making often requires many cycles because of bureaucratic procedures to approve access and modify datasets. This recurrent process involves multiple meetings across various layers of management, creating delays that may cause too much damage in the fast-paced AI era. In fact, the dynamic nature of AI-driven

applications demands immediate adaptability to market shifts. Consequently, the aforementioned delays can lead to missed business opportunities.

To address those challenges, the DATAMITE framework introduces a more agile and efficient approach. Its modular and data-product-driven architecture aims to replace the existing rigid and hierarchical governance model. The framework rids data governance of legacy constraints and also enables a more responsive and dynamic data-sharing ecosystem. In that way, DATAMITE empowers organizations to carry out rapid development and experimentation without compromising security and compliance. This shift ensures that organizations, such as OTE Group, can remain competitive in an environment where data-driven insights and AI applications must be deployed swiftly to capture emerging opportunities and maintain technological leadership.

5.2 Data Management Strategy in the era of AI

Besides a vertical implementation approach, AI adoption must also be structured in a horizontal way, to ensure that it is being incorporated into all company departments if it can be applied. To achieve this, a dedicated governing body or an appointed leader should oversee the orchestration of AI-driven initiatives, ensuring alignment with organizational objectives and building a coherent and robust data-driven ecosystem.

To this end, the Chief Data (Strategy) Officer (CDO) role within OTE Group, introduces a transformative approach on how to manage corporate data and extract value out of it. This pivotal position is in charge of the development and execution of a comprehensive data strategy that aligns with the organization's broader business objectives. The main duty of CDO is the deployment of strategic initiatives aimed at leveraging data to foster innovation, secure a competitive edge, and drive business growth [22].

CDO is also responsible for the establishment of robust data governance frameworks, policies, and processes. By instituting these elements, the CDO protects the integrity and privacy of data, and therefore mitigating risks and aligning with prevailing regulatory requirements. Furthermore, the CDO supervises the enhancement of the organization's data analytics capabilities. This task includes the implementation and usage of advanced analytics tools and methodologies to extract valuable insights from vast data repositories. Through those analytical endeavors, the CDO enables informed decision-making processes and also enhances the company's business intelligence capabilities. This leads to a gradual development of a data-driven culture within OTE Group [8].

To streamline data governance and management within such a complex enterprise, the CDO is set to introduce specialized versions of Data Marts tailored to the organization's unique needs. This approach ensures that each department's data requirements are extensively evaluated and fulfilled in alignment with the overarching data strategy.

5.3 DATAMITE Reference Architecture

The transition from traditional data management models to an advanced, AI-driven ecosystem requires a fundamental reshaping of existing architectures. The DATAMITE Reference Architecture (Figure 3) provides a complete framework to achieve this transformation smoothly, taking into account key challenges in data governance, security, and scalability. The DATAMITE framework aims at redefining data structuring, metadata utilization, and moving to a Data Product and Data Space paradigm. The goal is to help organizations enhance operational efficiency, simplify data accessibility, and boost real-time adaptability in an increasingly dynamic digital landscape.

Fig. 3. DATAMITE reference architecture

The core module that implements these concepts in the DATAMITE Reference Architecture (Figure 3) is the **Data Product Composition**. This module is designed to accept one or more datasets as input, enabling users to merge them into a unified file by comparing rows and columns or selectively retaining or removing specific attributes. More specifically, the module automatically analyses the input files, providing detailed metadata such as file names, column names, data types, the number of entries per field, and overall dataset size. In addition, it facilitates dataset comparison by examining structural similarities across columns and rows, enabling merging operations based on predefined criteria. Users have the flexibility to determine which columns should be retained or removed before finalizing the integration. Upon completion, the module generates and provides access to the merged dataset, ensuring a straightforward and efficient data processing workflow.

The DATAMITE reformation of the traditional two-layer approach (Figure 2) can be structured as a sequence of transformative steps. The first important step is the establishment of a unified data format that ensures consistency in

data governance, allowing for seamless restructuring and adaptation without dependence on external services. These services often introduce bottlenecks in data and security workflows, as they must continuously align with overarching processes while maintaining up-to-date policies and access controls. Furthermore, governance responsibilities are frequently fragmented among different entities, leading to inconsistencies in policy enforcement and security management.

The second critical step involves the implicit integration of metadata governance. Traditionally, metadata is managed at the database level rather than being centrally controlled through governance tools. This limitation results in fragmented data insights and restricts advanced data mining functionality. A unified approach to metadata governance would improve the accuracy and comprehensiveness of data analysis, facilitating better decision-making and more refined business intelligence models. By embedding metadata management into the governance framework, organizations can achieve greater transparency, improved data traceability, and greater automation of regulatory compliance.

The final and most significant step is the transition from a Data Mart oriented model to a Data Product and Data Space paradigm. In the traditional approach, Data Mart is optimized for specific tasks and serves as a well-structured repository for analytics and reporting. However, in alignment with the DATAMITE project's vision, Data Products are no longer limited to static repositories but instead evolve into dynamic, self-contained assets that incorporate governance mechanisms, live monitoring capabilities, and analytical tools. This shift enables real-time adaptability, ensuring that Data Products continuously align with business needs and regulatory requirements.

For example, in a typical business scenario in the telecommunications sector, when the call center department identifies a need for data sets related to customer satisfaction, loyalty and revenue metrics, the CDO -in collaboration with the Data Protection Officer (DPO)- uses a GUI to identify potential data sources. The needed information could be distributed across various repositories, such as customer, billing, and product databases. This approach allows for seamless data discovery, validation, and integration. The goal is to ensure that business users can access high-quality, policy-compliant datasets without delays caused by traditional bureaucratic procedures.

By adopting the DATAMITE reference architecture (Figure 3), organizations such as OTE Group can move towards a more agile, scalable, and policy-driven data ecosystem. The data there is not only a passive asset but an actively governed, continuously evolving resource. This paradigm shift promotes efficient data democratization, enhances cross-functional collaboration, and ensures that AI-driven applications can be deployed quickly and effectively.

Using tools such as Trino [21] for distributed data management, the CDO manipulates the GUI to select appropriate data columns from heterogeneous data sources (Figure 4), which meet the specific informational requirements, guided by company policies that demand selections based on quality and other criteria. For example, this process may involve, among others: accessing data considering sparsity thresholds (e.g. sparsity less than 10%), the inclusion of essential

Fig. 4. DATAMITE GUI for creating Data Products

contact information (e.g. at least one contact detail, based on the ontology that the meta-model has), considering the region or aging level (e.g. to be located in Greece where is allowed to offer services over 18 years old), enforcing compliance with GDPR for promotional purposes (has written consent for contacting for those purposes).

Upon finalizing the data selection, a corresponding Data Product is created to precisely address certain needs. This product is being strictly validated by the DPO as well as the security department, and then -if approved- is being made available for consumption in OTE's internal Data Product marketplace. There, it is accessible through the data catalog, allowing for tailored data visibility among different user groups within the organization. For example, call center personnel may be restricted to viewing only recent transactional data, whereas higher-level officials might access comprehensive customer histories. This is enforced at the run-time level through the access control mechanisms.

This innovative approach highlights the CDO's critical role in coordinating a more sophisticated data governance structure. The concept is to not only support strategic business objectives but also to ensure data privacy and compliance. In that way, it enhances OTE's position as a data-forward organization in the telecommunications industry.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

In the future, we intend to suggest a formalized procedure that will provide data handlers with a clearer idea of how data is gathered and used. This formalization will lead to improved data governance and data quality in general. Furthermore, we plan to integrate metadata on the maturity of services and datasets, taking into account that the performance of AI algorithms is highly dependent on those parameters. Our long-term goal is to leverage these best practices and workflows to apply them to other critical domains, such as healthcare. By doing so, the proposed architecture and design will progressively become more and more agnostic and generic to be able to easily adapt to many sectors of OTE Group's interest, beyond the telecommunications landscape [16]. This extension will not only prove our solution's adaptability, but will also contribute to the overall discipline of data management in a broad range of industries.

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